

Synthesis and characterization of piperazino-bis(methylantipyrine) and its complexes with chromium(III), manganese(II), cobalt(II), copper(II), zinc(II) and cadmium(II) ions

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A new Mannich base, piperazino-bis(methylantipyrine) (PBMA), was synthesized and characterized by spectral studies. Chelates of PBMA with chromium(III), manganese(II), cobalt(II), copper(II), zinc(II) and cadmium(II) ions were prepared and characterized by elemental analyses and IR, UV and ¹H NMR spectral studies. PBMA was found to act as a bidentate ligand bonding through one of the carbonyl oxygens of antipyrine and one of the C-N-C groups of piperazine moiety. Based on the magnetic moment values and UV-Vis spectral data, trigonal bipyramidal geometry for chromium(III), distorted octahedral geometry for copper(II) chloro and bromo complexes and tetrahedral geometry for cobalt(II), zinc(II) and cadmium(II) chloro and bromo complexes were assigned. TG and DTA studies show a double stage decomposition pattern for PBMA and its chromium(III), cobalt(II) and cadmium(II) chloro complexes and a single stage decomposition pattern for zinc(II) bromo complex. The kinetic and thermodynamic parameters for the thermal decomposition of the metal chelates were evaluated using equations based on integral methods. The antimicrobial studies show that the zinc(II) complexes are more active than the other complexes.

Antipyrine has a N-phenyl group and a -CH group on either side of a polar carbonyl group, thus resembling linkage-wise N-substituted amides. The carbonyl group in antipyrine is a potential donor due to the large dipole moment and strong basic character¹. In the metal complexes of antipyrine it is found to act as a monodentate ligand bonding through its carbonyl oxygen². Antipyrine and its metal complexes find applications in medicines³. In continuation of our work on Mannich base derivatives of antipyrine and their transition metal complexes⁴, in the present investigation we have reported the synthesis of a new Mannich base, piperazino-bis(methylantipyrine) and study of its interaction with the metal ions. An attempt is made to correlate the geometry, biological activity and thermal stability.

Results and discussion

PBMA is a white coloured solid and its melting point is 218°C and is recrystallised from ethanol. Percentage yield of the product is 82. The recrystallised product is analysed for C, H and N for checking the purity. The results of elemental analysis are given in Table 1. IR data with tentative assignments of various stretching and bending frequencies of PBMA are listed in Table 2.

The bands at 1668 and 1622 cm⁻¹ are due to the carbonyl stretching mode and absorption bands at 1176 and 1128 cm⁻¹ are due to the stretching of C-N-C of piperazine moiety. Pyrazolone ring stretching and bending appear at 1490 and 1473 cm⁻¹ respectively. Two new bands not found in the IR of antipyrine appear at 2950 and 2806 cm⁻¹ which are due to the insertion of piperazine moiety into the antipyrine ring and formation of PBMA. The ¹H NMR data are presented in Table 3. The signals at δ 3.32 and 3.04 ppm are assigned to >N-CH₃ and >C-CH₃ protons respectively. Phenyl protons appear as multiplet at δ 7.24–7.44 ppm. Further, the signals at δ 2.55 and 2.17–2.25 ppm are due to -CH₂-N< and -N(CH₂)₂ protons of piperazine ring respectively. The ¹³C NMR spectrum of PBMA shows two signals at δ 52.440 and 49.620 ppm corresponding to the substitution of -CH₂- and -N-(CH₂)₂ groups respectively. The ¹³C NMR signals are in agreement with the ¹H NMR data.

Elemental analysis (Table 1) shows the stoichiometry of the complexes as MX₂·PBMA for the anhydrous complexes and MX₂·PBMA·2H₂O for the hydrated ones. The chromium complex is [CrCl₃·PBMA]. Conductance measurement of 10⁻³ M solution of the complexes in DMF

Table 1. Observed and (calculated) percentages of elemental analysis and conductance data of chromium(III), manganese(II), cobalt(II), copper(II), zinc(II) and cadmium(II) complexes of PBMA (X = Cl or Br)

Complex	Metal	X	C	H	N	Λ_M^*
PBMA	–	–	69.09 (69.13)	7.00 (6.99)	17.26 (17.28)	–
CrCl ₃ .PBMA	8.04 (8.06)	16.56 (16.54)	52.13 (52.14)	5.26 (5.27)	13.02 (13.03)	24
MnCl ₂ .PBMA	8.99 (8.98)	11.56 (11.58)	54.90 (54.91)	5.56 (5.57)	13.72 (13.73)	61
CoCl ₂ .PBMA	9.56 (9.56)	11.49 (11.50)	54.54 (54.56)	5.50 (5.52)	13.63 (13.64)	55
CuCl ₂ .PBMA.2H ₂ O	10.23 (10.24)	11.42 (11.43)	54.14 (54.15)	5.47 (5.48)	13.48 (13.50)	45
CuBr ₂ .PBMA.2H ₂ O	8.94 (8.95)	22.52 (22.53)	47.35 (47.36)	4.77 (4.79)	11.83 (11.84)	55
ZnCl ₂ .PBMA	10.50 (10.51)	11.39 (11.39)	53.40 (53.99)	5.46 (5.46)	13.49 (13.49)	35
ZnBr ₂ .PBMA	9.11 (9.11)	22.46 (22.47)	47.23 (47.24)	4.77 (4.78)	11.80 (11.81)	47
CdCl ₂ .PBMA	16.79 (16.80)	10.58 (10.59)	50.19 (50.20)	5.07 (5.08)	12.54 (12.55)	55
CdBr ₂ .PBMA	14.01 (14.02)	22.06 (22.07)	44.30 (44.31)	4.47 (4.48)	11.07 (11.08)	58

PBMA = Piperazino-bis(methylantipyrine); * = Λ_M in $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ of $10^{-3} M$ DMF solution of the complex.

(Table 2) registers values in the range of 24–61 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ which indicates the complexes to be non-electrolytes.

From the elemental analysis, IR spectral, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectral data the structure assigned for PBMA is given in Fig. 1.

Chromium(III) complex of PBMA :

The comparison of the IR spectrum of the chromium(III) chloro complex with that of the ligand indicates the negative shifts for the carbonyl group as well as for C-N-C which points to the bidentate coordinating nature of the ligand. Even though the ligand is having four donor atoms, our studies reveal that irrespective of the metal, solvent and mole ratio, the ligand invariably behaves as a bidentate species only. Observance of two sets of values for $\nu_{\text{C-N-C}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ also indicates the same. Perhaps this behaviour may be due to the steric constraints, and the spatial disposition of donor atoms. Crystal structure determination would throw more light on this aspect. DRS spectrum registers weak bands at 10400, 13300, 17700 and 23250 cm^{-1} which are almost certainly *d-d* in origin, but their assignment is a matter of contradiction and the room temperature magnetic moment is 3.38 B.M. These observations⁵ suggest a trigonal bipyramidal structure for chromium(III) chloro complex as shown in Fig. 1.

Manganese(II) chloro complex of PBMA :

The IR spectrum of the compound registers bands at 1630 and 1587 cm^{-1} which are due to the $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ and the band at 1140 and 1076 cm^{-1} correspond to $\nu_{\text{C-N-C}}$. The above two vibrations suffer negative shifts when compared to their free ligand values. For the manganese(II) chloro complex absorption bands are observed at 25000 and 36000–35000 cm^{-1} . The latter intense and broad band originates from the charge transfer⁶. The stoichiometry in conjunction with the results of IR studies and the relatively intense electronic spectral bands suggest a tetrahedral geometry around manganese(II) in this complex.

Cobalt(II) chloro complex of PBMA :

The complex experiences negative shifts in the $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-N-C}}$ stretching frequencies. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ in the free ligand occurs at 1668 and 1622 cm^{-1} which are shifted to 1599 and 1556 cm^{-1} . The $\nu_{\text{C-N-C}}$ of the free ligand which occurs at 1177 and 1128 cm^{-1} are shifted to 1107 and 1078 cm^{-1} . DRS of this complex exhibits bands at 5840, 9605 and 16645 which are due to ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_2$, ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_2(F)$ and ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_2(P)$ transitions respectively. From the electronic spectral data collected for cobalt(II) chloro complex⁷, the frequencies ν_1 , ν_2 , ν_3 , β , $\beta\%$ and LFSE are found to be 5840, 9605, 16645, 584, 40 and 20 respectively. The per-

Table 2. Important IR absorption bands (cm^{-1}) of chromium(III), manganese(II), cobalt(II), copper(II), zinc(II) and cadmium(II) complexes of PBMA

Compd.	ν_{CH} in aromatics	New bands due to piperazine in cm^{-1}	Pyrazolone ring stretch	Pyrazolone ring bendmg	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	N-phenyl stretch	$\nu_{\text{C-N-C}}$ piperazine
PBMA	3246(m)	2950(s) 2806(s)	1491(s)	1473(m)	1668(s) 1622(s)	1190(w)	1177(s) 1128(s)
$\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot \text{PBMA}$	3421(b)	2908(s) 2858(s)	1495(s)	1440(w)	1599(s) 1562(s)	1180(w)	1134 1107
$\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot \text{PBMA}$	3258(b)	2930(s) 2840(s)	1490(s)	1470(w)	1630(s) 1587(s)	1190(w)	1140 1076
$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot \text{PBMA}$	3387(b)	2930(s) 2855(s)	1495(s)	1439(w)	1599(s) 1556(s)	1180(w)	1184(s) 1107(s)
$\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot \text{PBMA} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3350(b)	2901(b) 2868(s)	1500(b)	1432(w)	1660(s) 1626(s)	1190(w)	1133(s) 1077(s)
$\text{CuBr}_2 \cdot \text{PBMA} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3200(m)	2930(s) 2800(s)	1493(s)	1432(w)	1643(s) 1589(s)	1190(w)	1180(s) 1141(s)
$\text{ZnCl}_2 \cdot \text{PBMA}$	3130(s)	2998(s) 2934(s)	1496(s)	1460(w)	1640(s) 1589(s)	1180(w)	1142(s) 1109(s)
$\text{ZnBr}_2 \cdot \text{PBMA}$	3132(s)	2934(s) 2868(s)	1500(b)	1449(w)	1643(s) 1589(s)	1184(w)	1106(s) 1077(s)
$\text{CdCl}_2 \cdot \text{PBMA}$	3402(s)	2853(s) 2860(s)	1491(s)	1437(w)	1630(s) 1578(s)	1190(w)	1115(s) 1080(s)
$\text{CdBr}_2 \cdot \text{PBMA}$	3401(s)	2901(s) 2835(s)	1500(s)	1455(w)	1600(s) 1584(s)	1170(w)	1125(s) 1053(s)

PBMA = Piperazino-bis(methylantipyrine); s = sharp, b = broad, w = weak.

centage ionic character is found to be 40 and the μ_{eff} value is 4.43 B.M. Based on the above results, tetrahedral structure is assigned for cobalt(II) chloro complex.

Copper(II) complexes of PBMA :

The IR spectrum of the copper(II) chloro and bromo complexes show negative shifts in the carbonyl as well as C-N-C stretching frequencies indicating the bidentate coordinating nature of the ligand. The DRS of these complexes exhibit broad *d-d* absorption bands at 13512 and 11820 cm^{-1} respectively, which is due to $T_{2g} \leftarrow E_g$ transition and μ_{eff} values are 2.03 and 2.11 B.M. respectively. EPR spectrum of copper(II) chloro complex gives only one peak g_{iso} with a values of 1.860 which points to the presence of unpaired electron predominantly in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital.

EPR spectral data of copper(II) bromo complex viz. g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} , g_{av} , G and ω^2 are 2.120, 2.077, 2.118, 2.719 and 0.73 respectively. The copper(II) bromo complex shows $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$. The covalency parameter for this complex is 0.73 which indicates that the unpaired electron spends 27% of its time on the ligand donor atom. Based on the above results a dis-

torted octahedral geometry is assigned for copper(II) chloro and bromo complexes.

Zinc(II) and cadmium(II) complexes of PBMA :

The negative shifts for carbonyl group as well as for C-N-C are about 45–65 and 45–75 cm^{-1} respectively which points to the bidentate coordinating nature of the ligand. Small shifts can be due to the possible presence of solid state interactions, apart from being involved in coordination.

^1H NMR spectra of the d^{10} complexes are recorded in DMSO- d_6 and the δ values are shown in Table 3. The $-\text{N}(\text{CH}_2)_2$ protons of piperazine ring appear downfield at δ 2.27–2.51 ppm due to the electron drift towards the nitrogen, thus confirming that the tertiary amino nitrogen acts as a coordinating site. A downfield shift is observed in the case of $-\text{>C-CH}_2\text{-N<}$ protons which is probably due to the shielding zone created by the metal environment. The other protons appear almost in the same positions as in the free ligand. Based on the above observations tetrahedral geometry is proposed for the d^{10} complexes. The far IR

spectra of manganese(II), cobalt(II), copper(II) chloro complexes and copper(II) bromo complexes show absorption bands at 405, 355, 295, 390, 330, 440, 470, 350–380 and 297–295 cm^{-1} corresponding to Mn-O, Mn-N, Mn-Cl, Co-O, Co-N, Cu-O, Cu-N, Cu-Cl and Cu-Br stretching frequencies respectively⁵. The stretching frequencies at 430–460, 370–390, 300–340, 470, 381 and 314 cm^{-1} are assigned to the $\nu_{\text{Zn-O}}$, $\nu_{\text{Zn-N}}$, $\nu_{\text{Zn-X}}$, $\nu_{\text{Cd-O}}$, $\nu_{\text{Cd-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Cd-Cl}}$ vibrations respectively. Based on the physical data the structure of PBMA and the tentative structures of its complexes are given below :

Fig. 1. Structure of PBMA and its metal chelates.

Thermal decomposition studies and evaluation of kinetic parameters :

The TG of PBMA shows a double stage decomposition pattern. The decomposition temperature range for the first

and second stages are 375–425 and 425–625°C respectively. The exotherm at 557°C may be due to oxidative degradation of the ligand. The thermogram of $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot \text{PBMA}$ exhibits two stage decomposition pattern and the temperature ranges are 275–400°C and 425–625°C and the mass of the final residue does not correspond to any stoichiometric end product.

The TG pattern of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot \text{PBMA}$ shows a two stage decomposition pattern. The first stage slow decomposition starts at 300°C and terminates at 450°C, the mass loss corresponds to the elimination of the pyrazolone ring moiety (cal. 35.0%, obs. 34.0%). The second stage rapid decomposition starts at 525°C and it ends at 700°C. The mass of the final residue corresponds Co_2O_3 (cal. 27.0%, obs. 28.0%). An exothermic peak at 612°C points to the oxidative degradation of the organic moiety.

$\text{ZnBr}_2 \cdot \text{PBMA}$ is stable up to 275°C and the single stage decomposition temperature range is 300–600°C. The final mass of the residue as computed from the thermogram does not correspond to any stoichiometric zinc compound.

The thermogram of $\text{CdCl}_2 \cdot \text{PBMA}$ exhibits two stage decomposition pattern. The first stage slow decomposition temperature range is 250–450°C and the second stage rapid decomposition starts at 475°C and ends at 675°C. The mass of the final residue corresponds to CdO (cal. 19.2%, obs. 20.0%). An exothermic peak at 589°C shows the oxidative degradation of the organic moiety.

Evaluation of thermodynamic and kinetic parameters :

The kinetic and thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated using Coats-Redfern⁸ and Madhusudan-Krishnan-Ninan⁹ equations (Table 4). The order parameter is evaluated using a computer programme developed for the purpose. The value of order parameter n obtained by the above method is substituted in the C.R. equation used for kinetic studies. E and A are evaluated from the slope and intercept of the straight line respectively. The values of E , A , ΔS^\ddagger , ΔH^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger obtained for the decomposition stages are given in Table 4. The regression coefficient $R=1$ for the plot of L.H.S. of C.R. and M.K.N. equations vs $1/T$. The thermal decomposition was found to follow the first order kinetics. The negative values of ΔS^\ddagger show that the complexes are more ordered in the activated state than the reactants and the reactions are slow as indicated by a gradual mass change in the thermogram at the corresponding temperature.

In the majority of the cases the activation energies for the last stage of decomposition are higher than for all the

Table 3. ¹H NMR resonance signals for PBMA and its zinc(II) and cadmium(II) complexes

Compd.	Types of protons δ (ppm)				
	>N-C ₆ H ₅	>N-CH ₃	->C-CH ₃	->C-CH ₂ -N	N-(CH ₂ -CH ₂) ₂
PBMA	7.24–7.44(m)	3.32(s)	3.04(s)	2.55(s)	2.17–2.25(t)
ZnBr ₂ .PBMA	7.35–7.53(m)	3.35–3.44(s)	3.12(s)	2.63–2.97(s)	2.27–2.51(t)
CdCl ₂ .PBMA	7.35–7.51(m)	3.26–3.41(s)	3.11(s)	2.59(s)	2.28–2.52(t)

PBMA = Piperazino-bis(methylantipyryne); m = multiplet, t = triplet, s = singlet.

Table 4. Thermodynamic parameters for PBMA and its chromium(III), cobalt(II) and zinc(II) complexes

Compd.	Stage	CR				MKN			
		E _a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔH kJ ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG kJ ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	E _a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔH kJ ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG kJ ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
PBMA	I	87.00	-88.17	76.63	131.56	187.72	-87.72	76.95	131.59
	II	116.80	-93.23	102.99	180.38	117.19	-92.81	103.39	180.42
CrCl ₃ .PBMA	I	46.61	-154.18	37.42	122.68	46.99	-153.26	37.79	122.54
	II	96.33	114.07	83.70	170.40	96.75	-113.52	84.111	170.39
CoCl ₂ .PBMA	I	104.91	-69.46	96.11	136.08	106.23	-69.09	95.42	136.19
	II	174.27	-44.36	159.55	198.81	174.68	-44.14	159.97	199.03
ZnBr ₂ .PBMA	I	56.62	-152.00	45.88	144.07	57.02	-151.15	46.28	143.92
	II	69.54	121.70	59.81	131.011	69.87	-121.00	60.14	130.98

other earlier stages of thermal decomposition. The difference in the activation energy values for the various stages may be due to the different types of decomposition mechanisms operating at these temperature zones.

Biological studies :

The data on the percentage of bacterial growth are presented in Table 5. The inhibition in the growth of gram positive organism produced by various concentrations of the test compound is compared under identical conditions with the inhibition of the growth of the same by benzyl penicillin. Similarly, the inhibition of the growth of the gram negative organisms produced by the test compound is compared with those for different concentrations of streptomycin. In all the compounds tested for antimicrobial assay, it is found that activity increases with the increase in the concentration of the test compound. Among the various complexes, zinc(II) chloro and cadmium(II) bromo complexes are found to be the most active against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* respectively. This inhibition can be explained based on HSAB theory. The cadmium(II) is a soft acid and zinc(II) is border line. The important endogeneous ligating sites in the biological systems are O, N and S and their hardness sequence is O > N > S. Therefore, a hard metal prefers to bind to oxygen or nitrogen and soft metal prefers sulphur sites. The zinc(II) complex is coordinatively unsaturated and hence it exhibits tendency to bind with additional enzymatic-SH

groups. It was observed that higher the thermal stability of the metal complex higher is its antimicrobial activity.

Experimental

All the reagents used for synthesizing PBMA and its complexes were of A.R. grade and the solvents used were commercial products of the highest available purity and were further purified by standard methods.

Synthesis of PBMA and its metal complexes :

PBMA was synthesized by mixing 18.8 g of antipyryne (0.1 mol) with 9.2 mL of formaldehyde (0.1 mol) and 4.3 g of piperazine hydrochloride (0.05 mol). Piperazine hydrochloride was added to antipyryne-formaldehyde mixture at ice cold condition. The resulting mixture was stirred well and kept at room temperature for 24 h. A hard mass separated out which was washed with ether. The product obtained was dried in an air oven and crystallised from ethanol. The stoichiometry of the reaction can be represented as follows :

All the complexes were isolated from non-aqueous media. Chromium(III) chloro, manganese(II) chloro,

Table 5. Antimicrobial activity of PBMA and its chromium(III), copper(II), zinc(II) and cadmium(II) complexes against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*

Compd.	<i>E. coli</i>		<i>S. aureus</i>	
	Concentration (% inhibition)		Concentration (% inhibition)	
	24 h	48 h	24 h	48 h
PBMA	50 (57)	50 (79)	50 (59)	50 (87)
	100 (71)	100 (91)	100 (69)	100 (92)
	150 (72)	150 (93)	150 (73)	150 (94)
	200 (75)	200 (94)	200 (76)	200 (95)
	250 (75)	250 (93)	250 (71)	250 (94)
CrCl ₃ .PBMA	50 (18)	50 (80)	50 (52)	50 (86)
	100 (58)	100 (92)	100 (71)	100 (90)
	150 (70)	150 (92)	150 (72)	150 (93)
	200 (71)	200 (92)	200 (64)	200 (93)
	250 (72)	250 (92)	250 (64)	250 (94)
CuCl ₂ .PBMA.2H ₂ O	50 (62)	50 (81)	50 (89)	50 (94)
	100 (76)	100 (94)	100 (88)	100 (97)
	150 (78)	150 (94)	150 (94)	150 (97)
	200 (79)	200 (93)	200 (93)	200 (93)
	250 (77)	250 (94)	250 (93)	250 (93)
CuBr ₂ .PBMA.2H ₂ O	50 (55)	50 (87)	50 (79)	50 (84)
	100 (64)	100 (89)	100 (93)	100 (95)
	150 (68)	150 (92)	150 (93)	150 (95)
	200 (75)	200 (92)	200 (93)	200 (94)
	250 (71)	250 (90)	250 (93)	250 (93)
ZnBr ₂ .PBMA	50 (53)	50 (67)	50 (37)	50 (64)
	100 (74)	100 (89)	100 (64)	100 (88)
	150 (72)	150 (90)	150 (66)	150 (93)
	200 (74)	200 (92)	200 (64)	200 (94)
	250 (71)	250 (92)	250 (64)	250 (92)
CdCl ₂ .PBMA	50 (65)	50 (90)	50 (72)	50 (64)
	100 (68)	100 (93)	100 (92)	100 (94)
	150 (74)	150 (93)	150 (93)	150 (96)
	200 (75)	200 (93)	200 (93)	200 (97)
	250 (74)	250 (93)	250 (93)	250 (96)
CdBr ₂ .PBMA	50 (38)	50 (59)	50 (19)	50 (82)
	100 (79)	100 (92)	100 (72)	100 (96)
	150 (77)	150 (93)	150 (76)	150 (97)
	200 (88)	200 (93)	200 (77)	200 (98)
	250 (81)	250 (94)	250 (77)	250 (98)
Streptomycin	50 (70)	50 (98)	50 (52)	50 (81)
	100 (74)	100 (92)	100 (74)	100 (93)
	150 (80)	150 (92)	150 (77)	150 (94)
	200 (76)	200 (92)	200 (72)	200 (94)
	250 (77)	250 (93)	250 (74)	250 (94)

copper(II) bromo and zinc(II) and cadmium(II) chloro as well as bromo complexes were prepared by mixing the hot ethanolic solution of the respective metal salts with the ligand in 1 : 1 mole ratio. The complexes were obtained as precipitate, which were washed with hot ethanol and dried in a vacuum oven.

Cobalt(II) and copper(II) chloro complexes were prepared by dissolving the metal salt in acetone and the ligand in

chloroform. Green pasty mass obtained in the case of copper(II) salt was left aside at room temperature for 24 h and the resulting dark green product was filtered. The cobalt(II) complex was obtained as an insoluble precipitate. Both the complexes were washed with hot ethanol and dried in a vacuum oven.

The elemental analyses (C, H and N) were carried out using LECO-CHN 600. The electrical conductance mea-

measurements were carried out for the 10^{-3} M solutions of complexes in DMF at room temperature using a Systronics Direct Reading Digital Conductivity bridge-304 with a dip type conductivity cell.

The infrared and the far infrared spectral measurements were made for the ligand and its metal chelates using Perkin-Elmer 1430 Ratio Recording spectrophotometer and Bruker IFS 66V FT-IR spectrophotometer respectively. The electronic spectra of the complexes in the UV-Visible region were measured using JASCO UVIDEK 430 B double beam spectrophotometer using DMF as the solvent. The diffuse reflectance measurements (200–1800 nm) of some of the complexes were made on Cary 2390 spectrophotometer in magnesium carbonate medium.

The magnetic measurements of the complexes at room temperature were made by using Gouy magnetic balance. The Gouy tube was standardized using mercury(II) tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II).

Proton NMR spectra of the ligand and its d^{10} metal ion complexes were recorded using JEOL GSX 400 NB 400 MHZ FTNMR spectrometer using TMS as internal reference and DMSO- d_6 /CDCl₃ as solvent at ambient temperature.

A Varian E4-X-Band EPR spectrometer was used for recording the EPR spectra. The EPR spectra of powdered (polycrystalline) sample of the copper(II) complexes both at RT and LNT were studied at X band frequencies. Polycrystalline DPPH was used as a "g" marker. Simultaneous TG and DTA pattern of some of the complexes were recorded on Shimadzu Thermal Analyser DT-40 in an atmosphere of air at a linear heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ in the range of ambient - 1000°C using heated alumina as the standard reference material.

Antibacterial screening :

The tests were carried out using serial dilution technique. In this method, a nutrient broth medium containing 1% (w/v) peptone, 0.5% (w/v) yeast extract and 0.5% (w/v) sodium chloride was prepared in distilled water and sterilized by autoclaving for about 30 min.

A standard volume (10 mL) of the nutrient broth medium that would support the growth of the test organism was added to several labelled sterile stoppered identical assay tubes. A solution of each test compound was prepared in DMF and a series of dilutions were prepared using sterile pipettes. The concentrations tested were 50, 100, 150, 200 and 250 mg/mL of the compound under investigation, a wide spectrum antibiotic, the respective metal salt and

the blank (DMF). A control tube containing no test compound was included. Same quantity of the test organism from the broth culture was also added. All these operations were carefully carried out under aseptic conditions.

The assay tubes were inoculated at $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. The resultant turbidities at 24, 36 and 48 h were measured in a Nepheloturbidity meter. The measure of turbidity of the bacterial suspension is related to the bacterial growth inhibition produced by a foreign substance. The minimum inhibitory concentration of a test compound was the least concentration showing no visible turbidity. However, the percentage of bacterial growth inhibition produced by a particular concentration of the test compound was calculated from the measure of the turbidity of the control and turbidity of the particular test compound provided the impact of the solvent and the metal on the growth of the organism is negligible. The relationship used is : Inhibition = $(T_c - T_i / T_c) \times 100$, where T_c is the turbidity of the control and T_i is the turbidity of the specific compound or the test compound.

References

1. L. Reister, Jaques and Roland, *Pharmacology*, 1970, **3**, 243.
2. A. Kalbhen Dieter, P. Gelderblom and R. Domenjoz, *Pharmacology*, 1970, **3**, 353; Tsukioka Kinoko, Showa Igakkai and Zasshi, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1974, **84**, 84188; Naito Shunichi, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1970, **72**, 132721.
3. S. Viebel, E. Eggensen and S. L. Linholt, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1954, **8**, 763; Sherif Rawther and M. R. Gopala Krishnan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 117; J. Dick, R. Bacaloglu and A. Maure, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1967, **33**, 810; 1967, **12**, 607.
4. G. Boopathy, P. Kamalakannan and D. Venkappayya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 326.
5. G. Plesch, M. Blahora, J. Kratsmar and C. Friebol, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1987, **136**, 117; M. Ciampolini and G. P. Speroni, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1966, **5**, 45; F. Mani and L. Sacconi, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1970, **4**, 365; C. Simo and S. L. Holt, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 457; D. J. Machin, D. F. C. Morriss and E. C. Short, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 4658; D. H. Brown, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 3322; G. W. A. Fowles and P. T. Greece, *Chem. Commun.*, 1966, 784.
6. B. N. Figgis, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory", Interscience Publishers, New York, 1964.
7. A. Easwaran, "Introduction to Magnetochemistry", Interscience, New York, 1963; J. R. Ferraro, "Low Frequency Vibration of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Plenum, New York, 1971.
8. A. W. Coats and J. P. Redfern, *Nature*, 1964, **68**, 201.
9. P. M. Madhusudhanan, K. Krishnan and K. N. Ninan, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1986, **97**, 189.